

Upgrading SPHERE with the second-stage adaptive optics system SAXO+: Design and Assembly of the Near-Infrared Common Path and Wavefront Sensor Subsystem

Matteo Lombini^a, Emiliano Diolaiti^a, Eric Stadler^b, Laura Schreiber^{a,b}, Fausto Cortecchia^a, Yves Magnard^b, Sylvain Rochat^b, Adriano De Rosa^a, Giuseppe Malaguti^a, Didier Maurel^b, Gianluca Morgante^a, Filomena Schiavone^a, Alessandro Tacchini^a, Luca Terenzi^a, Markus Feldt^c, Markus Kasper^d, Norbert Hubin^d, Olivier Boebion^f, Anne Costille^e, Stephan Curaba^b, Kjetil Dohlen^e, Gael Chauvin^f, Florian Ferreira^g, Raffaele Gratton^h, Maud Langloisⁱ, Miska Le Louarn^d, Magali Loupiazⁱ, Johan Mazoyer^g, Julien Milli^b, David Mouillet^b, Mamadou N'Diaye^f, Sylvain Rousseau^f, Alain Spang^f, Michel Tallonⁱ, Fabrice Vidal^g, François Wildi^j, Gerard Zins^d, Anthony Boccaletti^g

^aINAF Osservatorio di Astrofisica e Scienza dello Spazio, via Gobetti 93/3, Bologna, 40129, Italy;
^bIPAG, Université Joseph Fourier-Grenoble 1, CNRS-INSU, Institut de Planétologie et
d'Astrophysique de Grenoble (IPAG) UMR 5274, Grenoble, F-38041, France; ^cMax Planck Institute
for Astronomy, Heidelberg, Germany; ^dESO, European Southern Observatory, Karl-Schwarzschild-
Str. 2, 85748 Garching bei Muenchen, Germany; ^eLAM, Laboratoire d'Astrophysique de Marseille,
CNRS/Aix-Marseille Université, Marseille, France; ^fLagrange, Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur,
UMR 7293, Bâtiment H. Fizeau, 28 Avenue Valrose, 06108 Nice Cedex 2, France; ^gLIRA,
Observatoire de Paris, Section de Meudon, 5 place Jules Janssen, 92195 Meudon Cedex, France;
^hINAF Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Vicolo dell'Osservatorio 5, 35122 Padova, Italy;
ⁱCRAL, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, ENS de Lyon, CNRS, Centre de Recherche
Astrophysique de Lyon UMR5574, F-69230 Saint Genis-Laval, France; ^jUniversity of Geneva, dépt.
d'Astronomie, Chemin Pegasi 51, CH-1290 Sauverny, Switzerland

*matteo.lombini@inaf.it

ABSTRACT

SAXO+ is the second-stage Adaptive Optics system developed as part of the SPHERE instrument upgrade at the ESO VLT, to improve high-contrast imaging capabilities for the detection and characterization of exoplanets and circumstellar disks. It also serves as a demonstrator for the Planetary Camera and Spectrograph of the European Extremely Large Telescope. SAXO+ is designed to operate downstream of the current SAXO extreme adaptive optics system. It provides moderate pupil sampling (about 25 actuators across the pupil) and high-speed correction (up to 2.76 kHz, with a target of 3 kHz), aimed at removing residual wavefront errors that limit contrast performance at small angular separations. The optical design is based on a switchable bypass architecture, where deployable fold mirrors divert the beam into the SAXO+ path and reinject it into the SPHERE optical train, preserving compatibility with existing scientific instruments. The module is compact, given the internal volume constraints, and it is designed for simplified installation and maintenance. It includes two internal pupil planes in the common path, hosting a deformable mirror and a deployable apodizer for coronagraphy, as well as a dichroic that feeds a modulated infrared pyramid wavefront sensor (wavelength range 0.950–1.450 μm). A fast-oscillating mirror provides tip-tilt modulation in the pupil plane along the wavefront sensor path. This contribution focuses on the Assembly, Integration, and Testing plan to be carried out at the INAF laboratories in Bologna. Particular emphasis is placed on the integration workflow, the design of the SPHERE simulator on the alignment bench, and the verification of the global alignment procedure of SAXO+ with respect to the SPHERE optical axis after installation at the telescope.

1. INTRODUCTION

High-contrast imaging from the ground has become one of the most powerful techniques for directly detecting and characterizing exoplanets and circumstellar environments. Instruments such as SPHERE [1] at the Very Large Telescope (VLT) have demonstrated the scientific impact of combining extreme adaptive optics (XAO), coronagraphy, and dedicated post-processing techniques, achieving contrasts on the order of 10^{-6} at separations of a few tenths of an arcsecond[2]. These capabilities have enabled significant discoveries, including the detection of new exoplanets and detailed studies of circumstellar disks, paving the way for the next generation of instruments.

After nearly a decade of successful operations, SPHERE is now undergoing a major upgrade to extend its scientific capabilities and serve as a precursor to future Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs). This upgrade, known as SPHERE+, has been designed to significantly improve the instrument's stability, sensitivity, and spectral coverage. The contrast gain will be enabled by a second-stage Adaptive Optics (AO) module [3] (hereafter, SAXO+), combined with the currently operating first-stage XAO system (SAXO). SAXO+ will provide moderate spatial sampling (in the range of 20–30 actuators across the pupil) and a fast correction frame rate (up to 3 kHz), measuring and reducing residual wavefront errors left uncorrected by SAXO. The second-stage opto-mechanical module is designed as a switchable optical bypass to preserve the current functionalities. Due to space constraints, it is compact yet ensures good accessibility for installation and maintenance. The optical interfaces at the output remain unchanged to guarantee compatibility with downstream scientific instruments. The module provides two internal pupil images for the second-stage deformable mirror and a deployable apodizer for coronagraphic observations. A dichroic feeds the second-stage infrared pyramid wavefront sensor[5].

The Assembly, Integration, and Test (AIT) strategy has been carefully planned to minimize risks and ensure reproducibility. The laboratory phase in Bologna includes step-by-step optical integration and alignment, verification of figures of merit through metrological and optical observables, and global alignment procedures designed to guarantee efficient installation at the telescope. This structured approach ensures that SAXO+ will meet SPHERE+'s stringent requirements.

In the following sections, we present the optical and opto-mechanical design of SAXO+, the conceptual design of the SPHERE simulator and its role in alignment and verification activities, and the AIT strategy defined for the laboratory phase, leading to integration at CRAL and the final installation at Paranal.

2. OPTICAL AND MECHANICAL DESIGN

SAXO+ will be installed on the SPHERE common path and infrastructure (CPI) bench using the existing holes. Since it was not possible to drill new holes into the SPHERE bench, the main challenge was to support this bench with only two legs (Figure 1). The structure has been optimized through Finite Element Analysis (FEA) to achieve the best stiffness-to-mass ratio. It will be built from aluminium 5083, the same material as the SPHERE bench, to avoid thermal differential effects. Due to the two-leg constraint, the first eigenfrequency does not reach 100 Hz but remains between 80 and 90 Hz. The final mechanical design was defined after the completion of the optical design. The optical tolerance analysis established all necessary adjustments and their ranges. The guiding principle of the mechanical design is to minimize the footprint on SPHERE while ensuring optimal accessibility.

The additional mass must be limited on the SPHERE bench and placed near the center of gravity to avoid perturbations of the Bilz active damping system. Considering that a recent upgrade (HiRISE)[3] was installed with a mass of about 50 kg, the added mass must remain below ~250 kg. SAXO+ is located very close to the center of gravity, and the total added mass on the SPHERE bench is about 125 kg.

A translation stage will deploy a fold mirror that diverts the optical beam from the SPHERE system to feed SAXO+ and then reinjects it into the original optical path, after the second-stage AO correction, through a second fold mirror (Figure xx). For optomechanical reasons, these mirrors and the final lenses for focal plane reimaging are mounted on a single deployment mechanism. When the group is retracted, SAXO+ is bypassed.

Figure 1: SAXO+ optomechanical design

Inside SAXO+, there are two optical paths (Figure 2): the common path (CP) and the wavefront sensor path (WP), which is fed by a beam splitter (BS). Most of the lenses (indicated as “lens”) are air-spaced doublets, except for one lens between the SAXO+ Double Pyramid prism (XPPY) and the final pupil images in the wavefront sensor, where an objective solution (XPOB) has been adopted to ensure sufficient back focal distance. The use of air-spaced lenses instead of cemented doublets avoids risks associated with thermally induced stress and light absorption from the glue.

The pyramid prism consists of two prisms made of different materials to reduce chromatic effects on the pupil images, following the approach already implemented in other AO systems[6]. This is the only cemented optical element inside SAXO+. The opto-mechanical design has been developed to fit into a small volume inside the SPHERE bench enclosure. The main components are located on a platform (called the “mezzanine”) above the SPHERE optical path.

Most components have static adjustments to be precisely positioned during the integration phases. Some components, such as pick-off mirrors, the apodizer, or dichroic beam splitters, require motorized movements to change the instrument configuration. In contrast, others require adjustment more or less frequently without manual intervention, which would be too complex and risky given the limited accessibility inside the SPHERE enclosure.

Motorized movements for the tilts of the two pick-off mirrors and the first internal folding mirror (respectively XPPOM1, XPPOM2, and XPFM1) have been added to allow seasonal adjustments and to facilitate the global alignment of SAXO+ to the SPHERE bench. SAXO+ is equipped with the Instrument Control Electronics (ICE), which enables remote control during the AIT phases and during normal operations, calibrations, and seasonal adjustments at the VLT.

Figure 2: SAXO+ optical model

3. ASSEMBLY, INTEGRATION, AND TEST FLOW

Figure 3 presents a simplified flow of the SAXO+ Assembly, Integration, and Test (AIT) process. The figure condenses the main phases of the workflow into key steps. The yellow boxes highlight the activities described in detail in this document, while the white boxes represent supporting or system-level activities. The following sections describe each step.

3.1 Components Delivery

The delivery will include all subsystems: mechanical structures, optics, deformable mirror (DM), and ICE. After local testing and validation at the various institutes responsible for the design and procurement of the subsystems, these components will be shipped to Bologna for the AIT phase.

3.2 SPHERE Simulator AIT

The first integration and testing phase will be carried out using the SPHERE simulator. This step validates the alignment procedures and verifies the alignment and performance of SAXO+ before shipment to CRAL for the system AIT.

SPHERE Simulator design

The SPHERE simulator was conceived as an optical and mechanical reference for the integration and verification of SAXO+ optical performance. Its purpose is to faithfully reproduce the SPHERE optical interfaces, such as f-number, focal length, and pupil geometry, while ensuring ease of use in a laboratory environment. This approach guarantees that the measurements performed in the laboratory are fully valid for the real instrument at the telescope.

Figure 3: Simplified AIT flow

The conceptual design of the SPHERE simulator includes: source, collimator, pupil stop, and objective. Starting from focal plane FP2, it reproduces SPHERE's FP3 focal plane with the same optical parameters, while providing sufficient space for the SAXO+ legs and folding mirrors within the optical path. The final design resulted from a trade-off analysis among different optical configurations. Solutions with custom and commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) optics were evaluated. The study considered the expected wavefront error, integration complexity, manufacturing costs, and laboratory reliability. It was found that COTS optics meet system requirements for wavefront error, offering lower costs and shorter delivery times. The Strehl Ratio at the exit focal plane remains above 90%, indicating that surface irregularities of the optics introduce only minimal degradations in image quality. This allows diffraction-limited performance to be maintained, making COTS optics a valid and cost-effective choice. For this reason, the final design of the simulator is based on COTS optics.

Key features of the Telescope simulator

- Unlike SPHERE, the visible dichroic and the ADC after FP2 are not included, as they are not needed for the alignment and testing phases of SAXO+. This reduces complexity and potential sources of misalignment.
- The entrance focal plane does not replicate the F/10 focal ratio of FP2 in SPHERE, since the baseline optical fiber (25 μm core) would have excessively degraded the Strehl Ratio. A focal ratio of f/55 was therefore adopted, resulting in negligible SR loss. The on-axis source can be shifted to simulate off-axis sources or replaced with a mask of regular holes to measure distortions and other observables useful during alignment.
- The collimator L1 is a COTS achromatic doublet with a focal length of 1000 mm.
- The pupil stop PS has a diameter of 16.98 mm, very close to the SPHERE pupil size. An insertable pupil mask is also foreseen, with calibrated holes to match different plate scales and pixel sizes for the output pupil image and the WFS camera, so that 2–3 pixel images can be obtained and pupil conjugation and alignment measured accurately.

- The objective L2 consists of two COTS lenses: a 1000 mm achromatic doublet and a 2000 mm singlet. Adjusting the distance between the two lenses yields the effective focal length needed to reproduce SPHERE's optical interface.
- The simulator must provide both an output focal plane (EFP) and an output pupil plane (EPP). The pupil plane is reproduced using an additional pair of doublets (L3). A technical laboratory focal plane (MATFP) is also included for alignment purposes. Two cascaded beam splitters (BS1 and BS2) simultaneously send light to the EFP, where a Hamamatsu camera (1000×1000 pixels, $5 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size) is located, to the EPP, where a C-RED3 (about 500×500 pixels, $15 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size) is located, and to the MATFP, where an alignment telescope is used for axial alignment of the components. Two reference pinholes along the optical path define the optical axis.
- The simulator must cover the spectral range $0.95\text{--}1.7 \mu\text{m}$. However, for polychromatic PSF evaluation, the range is limited to $0.95\text{--}1.45 \mu\text{m}$. Beyond $1.45 \mu\text{m}$, detector repositioning along the axis may be required to optimize focus.
- All opto-mechanical components are mounted on an L-shaped support plate, which will also host the SAXO+ legs. Threaded holes and kinematic stops are provided to ensure the precise repositioning of components in the event of removal. Folding mirrors keep the optical path within the bench dimensions. All opto-mechanical elements are mounted on linear stages for alignment and performance verification.

Figure 4: SPHERE simulator optical design

3.3 SPHERE Simulator requirements Verification

The simulator's output optical interfaces, both at the focal plane and pupil plane, will be validated through measurements of figures of merit, including optical quality, throughput, focal plane position, pupil plane quality, focal ratio, and pupil distance. These data will be used as references and compared with SAXO+ outputs during integration and at the end of alignment.

3.4 SAXO+ Mechanical and Electrical Integration

The integration of SAXO+ mechanics, cooling system, and electronics will be carried out in Bologna, after all components have been validated in the consortium's respective laboratories.

3.5 SAXO+ Metrological Alignment

Metrological alignment will be performed using the FAROARM instrument, which can determine the mechanical positions of surfaces and components with a precision of 0.02 mm . The measured data will be compared with the SAXO+

CAD model, and components will be repositioned if necessary. This procedure will also be repeated at the end of alignment and will serve as a reference for subsequent phases, particularly when SAXO+ is shipped to CRAL or to the telescope.

3.6 SAXO+ Optical (Re)integration and (Re)alignment

Optical integration and alignment will be performed step by step, using observables at both external and internal focal planes of the module.

The first step will align the common path optics and the internal folding mirrors. Next, the dummy deformable mirror will be aligned and used during the early phase before the real mirror is installed. Then the wavefront sensing channel will be aligned. Afterward, the lenses and lens groups of the common path will be integrated and aligned. Once mounted and axially aligned with the alignment telescope, figures of merit will be checked to monitor optical quality. This is expected to be an iterative process until requirements are met. Finally, the real deformable mirror and the apodizer will be mounted, aligned axially, and conjugated to the pupil. Once the optical integration and alignment are complete, the next natural step is to verify the Figures of Merit (FoM). This verification stage not only validates the quality of the achieved alignment but also establishes a quantitative reference for subsequent phases. In practice, FoM measurements serve as a bridge between optical fine-tuning and broader validation procedures. By comparing the results with those obtained using the SPHERE simulator, it becomes possible to assess whether the integration is proceeding correctly or if additional alignment iterations are required.

3.7 SAXO+ FoM Verification and SPHERE Simulator FoM Comparison

Verification of the figures of merit during SAXO+ alignment will be carried out at various stages, whenever feasible measurements are available. Each time, the results will be compared with the SPHERE simulator values to monitor whether integration and alignment are proceeding correctly or if steps need to be repeated or refined. At the end of the process, once integration and alignment are complete, a comprehensive verification of the figures of merit will be performed. This will confirm that the alignment requirements are met and provide a reference for subsequent phases of global integration and testing, up to installation at the telescope. These values will also be systematically compared with the simulator results, ensuring consistency and reliability throughout the validation process.

3.8 SAXO+ Global alignment verification

The global alignment process is a key step for telescope integration. After internal alignment, the module will be removed and re-mounted or shifted relative to the optical axis, to simulate telescope installation conditions. This allows the full global realignment sequence to be validated in advance. Global alignment refers to the three linear translations and three rotations around the center of the XPPOM1 mirror surface (Figure 2), which is defined as the origin of the coordinate system. Deviations are described as displacements along the main axes and tilts with respect to the optical axis. The procedure starts with high-precision metrological measurements to reconstruct the actual SAXO+ position, measured at the end of alignment. The mechanical degrees of freedom available on the leg where the pick-off mirror system is mounted allow for an initial manual correction. Alignment is then based on optical observables measured at the system output, including the PSF centroid position, pupil centering and rotation, DM centering, and pupil images on the WFS detector. The relationship between observables and the six global degrees of freedom is formalized through an interaction matrix, whose inversion provides a quantitative estimate of the misalignment vector. After identifying the errors, SAXO+ is re-centered with manual actuators. It is expected that SAXO+ can be aligned within errors of ± 0.33 mm in centering and ± 0.1 mrad in tilt. However, these corrections may introduce internal optical perturbations that must be compensated during fine alignment.

The fine alignment phase then follows, using internal and external observables, as well as the three motorized tilt mirrors (XPPOM1, XPPOM2, and XPFM1), to center the exit focal plane, the pupil plane, and the DM. Again, an interaction matrix links observables and degrees of freedom, enabling iterative corrections until residual misalignments are minimized.

This iterative scheme, combining coarse mechanical corrections and fine optical adjustments, ensures that SAXO+ can always be brought back within the required tolerances, even after disassembly or shifts. It is worth noting that the approach envisioned is very similar to that described for MAORY, which uses optical observables and interaction matrices to link global degrees of freedom to measured errors [7].

3.9 System AIT

This concerns the integration, testing, and verification of the entire SAXO+ system. After the AIT phase in Bologna, the system will be shipped to CRAL for additional activities and subsequently transferred to Paranal for installation at the telescope.

3.10 Internal Alignment Verification and Global Alignment on the SPHERE bench

Execution of alignment verifications directly on the SPHERE bench, including both internal and global alignment checks, to ensure proper operation once integrated. The activities described in Section 3.8 are intended to guarantee the success of this phase.

3.11 AIV / Commissioning

Final assembly, integration, and verification at Paranal, followed by the commissioning phase. This step validates the system's functionality in the real operational environment, under observing conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The SAXO+ subsystem represents a crucial step in upgrading SPHERE at the VLT, designed to enhance high-contrast imaging capabilities essential for detecting and characterizing exoplanets and circumstellar disks.

The work carried out so far has consolidated a robust design, capable of meeting the stringent volume and mass constraints imposed by SPHERE, while preserving the optical interfaces for downstream scientific instruments. The dedicated SPHERE simulator will play a fundamental role in validating alignment strategies and ensuring that laboratory measurements on SAXO+ are fully representative of on-sky performance. The simulator enables the verification of all figures of merit, including optical quality, throughput, and pupil conjugation, thereby reducing risks before final integration at the telescope. The alignment procedures will also ensure that the deformable mirror, the apodizer, and the wavefront sensor channel are conjugated to the required accuracy at their respective pupil planes.

The alignment procedures have been structured into sequential phases, combining metrological measurements with optical observables to achieve both coarse and fine alignment. The adoption of interaction matrices linking misalignments to measurable outputs has proven to provide a reliable framework for the iterative refinement of the system.

The integration of the mechanical, cooling, and electronic subsystems in Bologna provides a controlled environment for assembling and validating the system before it is shipped to CRAL and subsequently to Paranal. This staged approach ensures that each step, from laboratory verification to global alignment on the SPHERE bench, can be completed with well-defined checks and procedures in place.

In conclusion, SAXO+ has reached a mature level of design and integration planning, supported by detailed verification strategies and laboratory testbeds. The upcoming AIT phases will further strengthen confidence in the system's readiness for on-sky commissioning, paving the way for a significant improvement in SPHERE's adaptive optics performance while simultaneously providing a demonstrator for future instruments at the ELT.

Acknowledgments

The research activities described in this paper were carried out with contribution of the Next Generation EU funds within the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), Mission 4 - Education and Research, Component 2 - From Research to Business (M4C2), Investment Line 3.1 - Strengthening and creation of Research Infrastructures, Project IR0000034 – "STILES - Strengthening the Italian Leadership in ELT and SKA".

SAXO+ is an instrument designed and built by a consortium consisting of LESIA, CRAL, INAF, IPAG, Lagrange, LCF, University of Geneva, MPIA, and LAM, in collaboration with ESO. The SAXO+ project received funding from The Fondation Charles Defforey-Institut de France, CNRS/INSU, the Programme et Equipements Prioritaires de Recherche "Origins", the Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza, PlanetS, and MPIA.

REFERENCES

- [1] Beuzit, J. L., Vigan, A., Mouillet, D., Dohlen, K., Gratton, R., Boccaletti, A., Sauvage, J. F., Schmid, H. M., Langlois, M., Petit, C., Baruffolo, A., Feldt, M., Milli, J., Wahhaj, Z., Abe, L., Anselmi, U., Antichi, J., Barette, R., Baudrand, J., Baudoz, P., Bazzon, A., Bernardi, P., Blanchard, P., Brast, R., Bruno, P., Buey, T., Carbillet, M., Carle, M., Cascone, E., Chapron, F., Charton, J., Chauvin, G., Claudi, R., Costille, A., De Caprio, V., de Boer, J., Delboulb, A., Desidera, S., Dominik, C., Downing, M., Dupuis, O., Fabron, C., Fantinel, D., Farisato, G., Feautrier, P., Fedrigo, E.,

Fusco, T., Gigan, P., Ginski, C., Girard, J., Giro, E., Gisler, D., Gluck, L., Gry, C., Henning, T., Hubin, N., Hugot, E., Incorvaia, S., Jaquet, M., Kasper, M., Lagadec, E., Lagrange, A. M., Le Coroller, H., Le Mignant, D., Le Ruyet, B., Lessio, G., Lizon, J. L., Llored, M., Lundin, L., Madec, F., Magnard, Y., Marteau, M., Martinez, P., Maurel, D., Menard, F., Mesa, D., Möller-Nilsson, O., Moulin, T., Moutou, C., Origène, A., Parisot, J., Pavlov, A., Perret, D., Pragt J., Puget, P., Rabou, P., Ramos, J., Reess, J. M., Rigal, F., Rochat, S., Roelfsema, R., Rousset, G., Roux, A., Saisse, M., Salasnich, B., Santambrogio, E., Scuderi, S., Segransan, D., Sevin, A., Siebenmorgen, R., Soenke, C., Stadler, E., Suarez, M., Tiphene, D., Turatto, M., Udry, S., Vakili, F., Waters, L. B. F. M., Weber, L., Wildi, F., Zins, G., and Zurlo, A., "SPHERE: the exoplanet imager for the Very Large Telescope," *Astron. & Astrophys.* 631, A155 (2019)

- [2] Boccaletti A., Chauvin G., Wildi F., Milli J., Stadler E., Diolaiti E., Gratton R., Vidal F., Loupiau M., Langlois M., Cantalloube F., N'Diaye M., Gratadour D., Ferreira F., Tallon M., Mazoyer J., Segransan D., Mouillet D., Beuzit J.-L., Bonnefoy M., Galicher R., Vigan A., Snellen I., Feldt M., Desidera S., Rousseau S., Baruffolo A., Goulas C., Baudoz P., Bechet C., Benisty M., Bianco A., Carry B., Cascone E., Charnay B., Choquet E., Christiaens V., Cortecchia F., Di Caprio V., De Rosa A., Desrange C., D'Orazi V., Douté S., Frangiamore M., Gendron E., Ginski C., Huby E., Keller C., Kulcsár C., Landman R., Lagarde S., Lagadec E., Lagrange A.-M., Lombini M., Kasper M., Ménard F., Magnard Y., Malaguti G., Maurel D., Mesa D., Morgante G., Pantin E., Pichon T., Potier A., Rabou P., Rochat S., Terenzi L., Thiébaud E., Tallon-Bosc I., Raynaud H.-F., Rouan D., Sevin A., Schiavone F., Schreiber L., Zanutta A. "Upgrading the high contrast imaging facility SPHERE: science drivers and instrument choices", *Proc. SPIE 12184, Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*, 121841S (2022)
- [3] Vigan, A., El Morsy, M., Lopez, M., Otten, G. P. P. L., Garcia, J., Costes, J., ... & Soto, J. V. (2024). First light of VLT/HiRISE: High-resolution spectroscopy of young giant exoplanets. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 682, A16.
- [4] Stadler E., Schreiber L., Cortecchia F., Lombini M., Diolaiti E., Magnard Y., Rabou P., Rochat S., De Rosa A., Malaguti G., Maurel D., Morgante G., Schiavone F., Terenzi L., Chauvin G., Ferreira F., Gratton R., Hubin N., Kasper M., Langlois M., Le Louarn M., Loupiau M., Mazoyer J., Milli J., Mouillet D., N'Diaye M., Rousseau S., Tallon M., Vidal F., Wildi F., Zins G., Boccaletti A. "Upgrading SPHERE with the second-stage adaptive optics system SAXO+: conceptual design of the opto-mechanical module," *Proc. SPIE 13097, Adaptive Optics Systems IX*, 130976S (2024).
- [5] Ragazzoni, Roberto. "Pupil plane wavefront sensing with an oscillating prism." *Journal of modern optics* 43.2 (1996): 289-293.
- [6] Tozzi, A., Stefanini, P., Pinna, E., & Esposito, S. (2008, July). The double pyramid wavefront sensor for LBT. In *Adaptive Optics Systems* (Vol. 7015, pp. 1454-1462). SPIE.
- [7] Patti M., Lombini M., Redaelli E.M.A., and Diolaiti E. "Simulating the optical alignment of the multiconjugate adaptive optics module for the extremely large telescope," *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems* 5(1), 018005 (2019).